

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
College of Engineering
MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT
Estancia, Iloilo

Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer

A Project Study

Presented to

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APPROVAL SHEET

This project study entitled "Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer" prepared and submitted by Elton B. Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto, and Saimon Aldrich A. Mora in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering has been examined and is hereby recommend for approval and acceptance.

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INTEGRATED COCONUT SHELL CARBONIZER-PULVERIZER

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on addressing the need for a practical and sustainable solution for processing coconut shell waste through the development of the *Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer*. Designed to simplify and improve the processes of carbonization and pulverization, the device integrates two distinct operations into a single machine.

The design was guided by prior arts, particularly *Charcoal Production in 200-Liter Horizontal Drum Kilns* by

Rick Burnette, which emphasized staged heat management and accessible construction methods, and the *Covered Cavity Kiln Pyrolyzer* (US11254875B2), which introduced rotational heat exposure and modular combustion. The pulverization mechanism also drew reference from the *Hammer Crusher with Automatic Exhaust Function* (CN214131912U) and the *Ruminant Arch Type Hammer Mill* (CN216856947U), contributing to the development of the machine's crushing and sifting features.

The performance of the device was evaluated through three trials using 10 kg, 15 kg, and 20 kg of coconut shells. The carbonization process recorded an average processing time of 39.3 minutes, yielding an average of 3.99 kg of charcoal. The pulverization phase achieved a mean processing time of 17.6 minutes, producing an average of 3.6 kg of pulverized charcoal. The device's design received a "Highly Acceptable" rating with a weighted mean of 4.52, while its capability achieved a rating of "Excellent" with a weighted mean of 4.58. These findings indicate that the *Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer* is a reliable and safe option for small- to medium-scale use. The study concludes that the device addresses the limitations of traditional charcoal production by reducing manual labor, improving output consistency, and supporting safer operational practice.

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Chapter I

Introduction

Background of the Study

Coconut shell, an abundant agricultural waste in tropical countries like the Philippines, is often underutilized despite its potential as a renewable resource. The growing agricultural activities in the Philippines have exceeded the capacity of natural decomposition processes, leading to increased accumulation of coconut shells as waste (Alejano et al., 2024). In regions such as Aklan and Iloilo on Panay Island, initiatives to utilize coconut shells for producing charcoal briquettes have been implemented. However, traditional methods like pit burning result in low-quality charcoal contaminated with soil and other impurities, while emitting harmful smoke that poses health risks (Hernandez, 2024). One such area experiencing these challenges is the Municipality of Barotac Viejo, Iloilo.

Coconut shells, with a high calorific value of 20.8 MJ/kg, are ideal for producing steam, biochar, and energy-rich gases through pyrolysis, a process that converts biomass into valuable products. These shells are particularly suitable for pyrolysis because they contain

low ash content and high volatile matter, making them a cost-effective and efficient fuel source. However, conventional methods of charcoal production, such as pit burning, often lead to inconsistent results due to uneven heating and contamination from external materials (Shuliy, 2024).

The traditional process of converting coconut shells into charcoal presents several significant risks. One major concern is the use of open-pit carbonization, which generates harmful gases such as carbon monoxide (CO), posing serious health hazards to workers through prolonged exposure. Additionally, the manual handling of hot charcoal during and after carbonization increases the risk of burns and other heat-related injuries. Inconsistent cooling methods, such as pit cooling, can also lead to variations in charcoal quality, which may compromise product safety and reliability (Flora Charcoal, 2020; FAO, 2024).

To address these challenges, integrating the processes of carbonization and pulverization offers a more efficient and safer alternative. By utilizing technologies that allow for simultaneous carbonization and pulverization, producers can streamline production, reduce health hazards, and achieve better control over product quality. This integrated approach not only aims to enhance efficiency but

also minimizes the risks associated with open-pit methods, such as harmful emissions and uneven heating, while promoting sustainable practices in biomass utilization.

This study aims to, integrated coconut shell carbonizer and pulverizer that will improve the efficiency and safety of charcoal briquette production. Specifically, it aims to reduce operational costs, improve product consistency, and ensure the safety of workers in the charcoal briquette production industry.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this project is to design, develop, evaluate and test the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer.

Specifically, this study aims to:

a. Evaluate the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer as to its design.

b. Determine the burning duration and quantity of coconut shells that can be carbonized.

c. Determine the operational speed of the pulverizer and the quantity of carbonized coconut shell if it is capable of pulverizing.

Conceptual Framework

In order to give clearer understanding to the study, the conceptual framework is hereby presented. The study follows the input-throughput-output approach as shown in the paradigm in figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1 Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1.1 Shows the concept of how this kind of research study was conducted. The input stage is composed of prior arts, concepts, ideas, methods, tools, and equipment. The throughput stage consists of fabrication, technical evaluation, revision, and data gathering and analysis. After successful revision, the output stage is

the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer. Along with the input, throughput, and output are the feedback to be accepted.

Definition of Terms

Academe. Is the community and scholarly environment within an institution of higher education, and it's more often called "academia."

In this study, "academe" means a group of evaluators coming from the education sector, especially the faculty from BSME Department of Northern Iloilo State University.

Agricultural Waste. Is defined as waste left over after cultivating and processing agricultural products like fruits, vegetables, dairy and grains, as well as meat, poultry and crops.

In this study, "agricultural waste" refers to the unwanted parts of crops, such as coconut shells, that can't be used for human or animal consumption.

Biochar. Is a stable solid, rich in carbon, that is made from organic waste material or biomass that is partially combusted in the presence of limited oxygen.

In this study, "biochar" is the outcome or product produced after the process of pyrolysis and will be interchangeably used with carbonized coconut shell.

Carbonizer. A machine or device that carries carbonization.

In this study, the carbonizer will be the component responsible for partially burning coconut shells and producing charcoal.

Coconut Shell. Are the hard outer layer or husk of a mature coconut fruit. They are typically brown in color and have a fibrous, woody texture. The shells are derived from coconuts that have been harvested and had their inner flesh removed.

In this study, "coconut shells" will be used as the material in operating the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer.

Design. Is the process of envisioning and planning the creation of objects, interactive systems, buildings, vehicles, etc.

In this study, "design" refers to the intended structure and the individual functions of each part of the machine.

Evaluation. Is the act of determining the value, nature, character, or quality of something or someone.

In this study, "evaluation" will be referred to as the process of determining the performance and ability of the machine to accomplish this study's objectives.

Flap. A flat piece of material that is attached to something on one side and that can be easily moved.

In this study, "flaps" refer to flat bar attachments that serve as blades, functioning to crush and pulverize the biochar through impact force.

Pit Burning. A pit dug into the ground or encased in a surrounding structure (as of masonry or steel) in which a fire is kept burning for cooking, warmth, etc.

In this study, "pit burning" refers to the traditional method of producing charcoal. Despite being less efficient, hazardous, and ecologically unfriendly, it's still widely used today, particularly in rural areas.

Pulverizer. The one who or that which pulverizes; especially, a machine for breaking the soil, crushing stone, grinding grain, etc.

In this study, the pulverizer is the machine that will be responsible for turning coconut shell charcoal into fine powder.

Pyrolysis. The chemical decomposition of organic (carbon-based) materials through the application of heat.

In this study, "pyrolysis" is referred to as the process of thermally decomposing the organic material in the absence of oxygen.

Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer. Refers to the combination of two separate devices into a single machine capable of performing both carbonization and pulverization processes.

In this study, *Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer* refers to the title of the project study conducted by students from the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Northern Iloilo State University.

Significance of the Study

This research study will bring great benefits for the following:

Local Charcoal Briquette Producers. The Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer will be extremely beneficial to local charcoal briquette makers since it provides an innovative solution to their issues with efficiency, safety, speed, and sustainability. The device not only improves manufacturing efficiency, but it also reduces waste and emissions, making it an ecologically friendly solution.

Coconut Milk Vendors. This study will be beneficial to coconut milk vendors since it would provide a means for them to dispose of their unwanted waste, which is essentially useless to them, by selling it to charcoal

briquette makers. This collaboration will reduce waste products while also providing an extra source of income for the vendors. Furthermore, it would help to create a more sustainable environment by encouraging recycling and innovative waste management systems.

Copra Farmers. This study will benefit the farmers economically since the integrated coconut shell carbonizer-pulverizer utilizes coconut shells. It uses agricultural waste as raw material to make an ecologically beneficial product. This device will be an alternative way to dispose waste on coconut farms and avoid pit burning or traditional charcoal production since it reduces smoke emissions and air pollution.

Future Researchers. The findings of this study will serve as a foundation for the development of innovative tools and equipment that maximize agricultural waste processing possibilities while also encouraging sustainability. This study aims for advancements in renewable energy and waste reduction, with a particular impact on the coconut industry.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This device will be tested according to its design, capability, and performance. This study will be conducted

and examined by experts from the Mechanical Engineering Department of Northern Iloilo State University, Estancia, Iloilo.

The device has a Carbonizer that is designed specifically for carbonizing coconut shells, and a Pulverizer with the specific purpose of crushing biochar into fine powder. The result will be given to the briquette producer of Brgy. Vista Alegre, Barotac Viejo, Iloilo to maximize the production to suit local demand, preferences, and environmental considerations.

Meanwhile, total carbonization may be difficult to achieve, leading to incomplete conversion of organic material. This can result in lower efficiency and leaving behind uncarbonized residues. Consequently, this can compromise the integrity of the device and necessitate frequent maintenance. To mitigate these issues, careful control of carbonization is essential, ensuring that the coconut shells are treated to optimize conversion and minimize residue.

Carbonization in this study is conducted using a steel drum method, where cleaned and dried coconut shells are loaded into the drum and subjected to continuous burning with an open feeder supplying oxygen. Although the carbonizer has a capacity of 20 kg, it should not be fully

loaded, as this may result in incomplete combustion. The process involves initially loading a small quantity of coconut shells, followed by gradual loading of the remaining shells during combustion. After all the material is burned, the feeder and chimney are closed to cut off the oxygen supply, allowing carbonization to complete. The drum is then left to cool for approximately an hour. The resulting charcoal is lightweight, porous, and high in carbon content, with a high calorific value and minimal smoke emission. This study is limited to the processing and evaluation of coconut shell charcoal produced using the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer, excluding other biomass or charcoal types.

Chapter II

Review of Related Literature

This chapter presents the related studies and prior arts on which the project study was based. It also presents the theories on designing the device and principles regarding the carbonizer and pulverizer.

Related Studies

This related study forms the basis of the project study, along with relevant theories on device design and carbonization principles. The nearest related study is "Coconut Shell Carbonization Process Using Smokeless Kiln" by Arief et al. (2023), explored and designed a smokeless kiln to optimize charcoal production from coconut shells. Their study revealed that a 25 kg capacity kiln could produce up to 12 kg of charcoal within 150 minutes, resulting in a 48% yield. This outcome highlights the potential of this innovative approach for achieving substantial productivity in a short period, particularly when the kiln is operated at full capacity.

The study also explored varying capacities, showing that burning 15 kg of coconut shells yielded 6 kg of charcoal (40%), while 20 kg produced 9 kg (45%). These results suggest that a full 25 kg load not only maximizes yield but also optimizes fuel use, as higher capacities experience less heat loss during the process. This kiln design demonstrates an effective solution for small-scale, sustainable charcoal production from coconut shells, aligning with local economic and environmental objectives.

Furthermore, the findings indicate that utilizing the maximum capacity of the kiln significantly enhances charcoal yield and reduces operational inefficiencies. This development could be advantageous for small businesses or home industries focused on producing coconut shell charcoal. The kiln's practical design, based on recycled steel drums, and its efficiency in converting coconut shells to charcoal underscore its potential for broader application in regions where coconut shell waste is abundant.

Another nearest related study discusses the process of carbonization in a 200-liter drum kiln. The article, titled "*Charcoal Production in 200-Liter Horizontal Drum Kilns*", published by Rick Burnette in 2016, details both the construction and operational processes of horizontal drum kilns specifically designed for small-scale charcoal

production. This method aims to provide accessible technology for converting small-diameter wood and agricultural residues into charcoal while also capturing wood vinegar, a useful by-product in farming.

Burnette's study elaborates on constructing a 200-liter drum kiln, highlighting materials and techniques for achieving optimal carbonization. The technology allows for the use of small, readily available biomass, such as branches, bamboo, rice straw, and other farm residues, making it highly suitable for communities with limited access to larger fuel wood sources.

The process of carbonization in the drum kiln involves stages of carefully managed heat to break down woody material into charcoal. As noted in *Industrial Charcoal Making* (FAO), carbonization requires five stages of heat management, starting from initial drying and decomposition to high-temperature refinement around 500°C, producing quality charcoal with minimal ash.

Burnette's document shows that the 200-liter kiln's design enables effective carbonization of bamboo, making it a renewable alternative for fuel production in regions where bamboo is abundant.

After sealing the flue and outer vent, kiln operators shift the insulating soil or sand from on top of the kiln to the retaining wall, allowing the kiln to cool. This cooling period, which lasts 12 to 15 hours, is essential to complete carbonization without igniting the charcoal. After cooling, the finished charcoal can be removed from the kiln, ready for packaging or storage. This final step highlights the simplicity and sustainability of the 200-liter drum kiln, providing local communities with a viable resource management and energy solution.

Prior Art

The closest prior art entitled "Covered Cavity Kiln Pyrolyzer", invented by Anderson Paul S.; Gilmore Gary L., published on 2022-2-22 Publication of US11254875B2, shown in Figure 2.1. The invention presents a covered cavity kiln pyrolyzer with modulated means of rotation, to promote mixing and exposure of the biomass to heat, thereby allowing complete and efficient pyrolysis of biomass therein. The invention has a portal arrangement for simultaneous entry of fuel and air alongside the exit of emissions and flames to a separate hood structure. In addition to rotational modulation for mixing, the rotational capabilities of the kiln also permit the removal of processed charcoal when the portal is turned downward. The

invention also has a system of internal prongs for mixing and sifting removal of char, as well as automated fuel delivery mechanisms and a system of openings to allow insertion of pipes and sensors into the kiln for monitoring and for additional delivery of reagents for better modulation and efficiency by a user during the pyrolyzation process.

Figure 2.1 "Covered Cavity Kiln Pyrolyzer"

Another prior art was invented by WU JIAHE; WU JIAJUN, published on 2021-09-07, Publication of CN214131912U, entitled "Hammer Crusher with Automatic Exhaust Function" shown in Figure 2.2. The hammer mill with the automatic

exhaust function comprises a base and a limiting block, a connecting plate is installed above the base, an installing plate is arranged above the connecting plate, a driving motor is installed in the installing plate, a first bearing is arranged on one side of the driving motor, and a second bearing is arranged on the other side of the driving motor. A connecting rod is connected to the front end of the driving motor, a connecting shell is arranged on one side of the connecting rod, a clamping hoop is arranged on one side of the connecting shell, a pulverizer shell is arranged on the other side of the connecting shell, a feeding port is formed in the upper portion of the pulverizer shell, and a discharging port is formed in the lower portion of the pulverizer shell. According to the hammer mill with the automatic exhaust function, after being started, the driving motor can drive the connecting rod to rotate, equipment is driven to operate, the first bearings are installed on the two sides of the connecting rod, the driving motor is also provided with the first bearings, it is guaranteed that the equipment can operate smoothly, and stability is improved.

Figure 2.2 "Hammer Crusher with Automatic Exhaust Function"

Another prior art was invented by Zhiyou et al., published 2022-07-01, Publication of CN216856947U entitled "Ruminant Arch Type Hammer Mill" shown in Figure 2.3. The utility model discloses a ruminant arch type hammer mill, and particularly relates to the technical field of mills, the ruminant arch type hammer mill comprises a mill feed port, the bottom end of the mill feed port is communicated with a mill shell, and a crushing mechanism is mounted in the mill shell; and the crushing mechanism comprises a feeding guide plate arranged in the crusher shell, a first crushing screen is connected to the bottom end of the feeding guide plate, a plurality of first crushing holes are formed in the inner

wall of the first crushing screen, and a first rumination arch is connected to the bottom end of the first crushing screen. The crushing mechanism is adopted, crushed materials are discharged along a plurality of second crushing holes in a second crushing screen, a circulation layer of the materials is damaged by ruminant arches during crushing each time, the movement direction of particles is changed, the relative speed of a hammer and the materials is increased, the crushing efficiency of the materials is improved, forward and reverse driving crushing can be achieved, and the crushing efficiency is improved. And the equipment is more convenient to use.

Figure 2.3 "Ruminant Arch Type Hammer Mill"

Synthesis

The design and development of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer drew inspiration from multiple studies and prior arts focused on the enhancement of coconut shell carbonization and pulverization technologies. The data of the Drum Kiln was based on Arief et al. (2023) study that explored the optimization of coconut shell carbonization using a smokeless kiln and achieved a charcoal yield of 48% from a 25 kg load over a carbonization period of 150 minutes. The shape and the orientation of the drum has based inspiration from Burnette's work on 200-liter horizontal drum kilns provided further insight into small-scale charcoal production. His approach emphasized affordability, ease of use, and localized construction using readily available materials. Burnette detailed how horizontal kilns, when properly managed, could produce high-quality charcoal with minimal smoke, using methods that were accessible to rural communities.

The concept of proper air inlet for oxygen intake and design was based on the nearest prior art from Anderson and Gilmore (2022) named "Covered Cavity Kiln Pyrolyzer," which is focused on rotational modulation within a horizontal kiln. This innovation aimed to enhance heat distribution and improve the uniformity of carbonization across the biomass

load. Their system was designed to prevent uneven exposure to heat, which often leads to under-carbonized residues and reduced charcoal quality.

The pulverizer component of the integrated device was similarly influenced by key prior arts. The "Hammer Crusher with Automatic Exhaust Function" by Wu Jiahe and Wu Jiajun (2021) presented a robust mechanical system for biomass pulverization. Further performance improvements were informed by the "Ruminant Arch Type Hammer Mill" developed by Zhiyou et al. (2022). Their design incorporated a feed guide plate and multi-hole crushing screens that promoted rapid material flow and efficient crushing action. The decision to integrate both carbonizing and pulverizing functions into a single unit drew further inspiration from the broader need to streamline post-harvest biomass processing in agricultural contexts.

Chapter III

Methodology

This chapter presents the Description of the Device, Fabrication Procedure, Gantt Chart, Test Procedure, Pilot Testing and Revision, Technical Evaluation and Revision Instrumentation, Validation Procedure for Instrument, The Respondents, Operation Parameters, Data to be Gathered, Statistical Data Analysis, and Cost Analysis.

Description of the Device

The Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer is an innovative device designed to efficiently convert coconut shells into fine carbonized powder. It consists of two main components: a carbonizer and a pulverizer. The carbonizer is a horizontal drum kiln equipped with fabricated hatches and exhaust systems to promote even heat distribution. It has a 100-liter capacity and can hold up to 20 kg of coconut shells.

The pulverizer is fitted with 20 blades attached to a motor-driven shaft powered by a 1.5 hp motor using a B50 V-belt. The blades are welded with angle and flat bars functioning like hammer heads to crush the carbonized shells into fine powder suitable for charcoal briquette production.

Both components are securely mounted on a sturdy angle bar frame to provide stability, durability, and safety. The carbonizer is fixed atop the frame for added stability, while the pulverizer is bolted for easy removal during maintenance.

During operation, coconut shells are loaded into the carbonizer feeder until the 20 kg capacity is reached. The shells are ignited and burned, after which the feeder hatch and exhaust are closed to cut off the oxygen supply and initiate the carbonization process. Once cooled, the carbonized shells are discharged through the bottom hatch and transferred to the pulverizer feeder. Inside the motor-driven pulverizer, the shells are ground by rotating blades into fine powder, which then exits through a strainer and discharge outlet for collection. The device's fabrication followed detailed isometric specifications, ensuring efficient performance and durability.

The figure below shows the isometric view with specifications which were the basis of the fabrication of Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer.

Figure 3.1 Isometric View of Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer

Fabrication Procedure

In the stage of planning design, the researcher spent considerable time and effort reviewing the features of the existing prior art, to decide as to what materials are needed and to be used to fabricate the device. The design plan of the device was prepared right after the analysis. Next, the materials and supplies needed were prepared and reviewed based on the needed specifications to ensure durability and effectivity, fabrication of the device was initiated based on the specified design in the drawing plan. There are some of the factors of fabrication that may consider including production cost, workmanship and materials to ensure that it is safe and its reliability according to the industry standard and as well as suitable to its purpose of operation.

Gantt Chart

The table shows the progress of the construction, fabrication, pilot testing, and revision of the Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer from January 6, 2024 to March 3, 2025. The average working time during fabrication process in a whole week was 2 hours a day.

Test Procedure

The researchers will formulate the following test procedure in terms of its performance, and design:

1. The device will

- a. undergo technical evaluation and revision.

- b. be evaluated by the technical evaluators using the validated questionnaire

- c. be evaluated in terms of its design by the respondents using the validated questionnaire from the following:

- c.1 Experts from the Academe

- c.2 Briquette Makers

2. The researchers will determine the burning duration in minutes and quantity in kilograms of carbonized coconut shells.

3. The researchers will determine the operational speed of the pulverizer and the quantity of carbonized coconut shells pulverized.

Pilot Testing and Revision

Following its development, the device underwent a pilot test to identify any defects, operational difficulties, and flaws observed during the operation. The device was open to comments made by the evaluators during

this phase of the process. The data was gathered using a research-made questionnaire, specifically to establish the tool's capabilities and design parameters.

Technical Evaluation and Revision

The device was presented to the study participants and an expert panel for technical evaluation consisting of evaluators from the experts of the academe and the community abundant in coconut shells in order to obtain the required feedback regarding suitability for functionality, design, and performance.

Instrumentation

The Development of the Instrumentation

For this study, a series of questions was created. The data was gathered from the results of a research instrument used to determine acceptability during the acceptability evaluation. The questionnaire tool was created by the researcher, and it was gone through approved procedures for validity assessment. The researchers' acceptability evaluation instrument/ questionnaire was composed of 20 items with 5-point Likert Scale, ten (10) for design and ten (10) for capability. Each item in the acceptability evaluation in terms of the design were checked by the

respondent according to his/her response as to its statistic type of ordinal measure which were "Not Acceptable" (NA), "Slightly Acceptable" (SA), "Moderately Acceptable" (MA), "Acceptable" (A), and "Highly Acceptable" (HA) as shown in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2. *Present the Scale of Level of Acceptability in Terms of Design*

Scale	Description
5	Highly Acceptable
4	Acceptable
3	Moderately Acceptable
2	Slightly Acceptable
1	Not Acceptable

Each item in the arbitrary scale level evaluation in terms of the capability were checked by the respondent according to his/her response as to its statistic type of ordinal measure which were "Very Poor" (VP), "Poor" (P), "Good" (G), "Very Good" (VG), and "Excellent" (E), as shown in Table 3.3.

Validation Procedure for Instrument

The research instrument was designed to measure the acceptability of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer, in terms of its design and performance, was submitted to the panel of examiners for validation. The examiners were composed of four (4) experts from the faculty of Mechanical Engineering and one (1) English critique.

Validity commonly defined as the most important consideration in test evaluation. The concept refers to the appropriateness, meaningfulness and usefulness of the specific inferences made from test scores validity, however is a unitary concept. Although evidence may be accumulated in many ways, validity always refers to the degree to which that evidence supports the inferences that are made from test scores (Braun, H. et al. 2013)

The Respondents

The respondents of this study were five (5) experts from the academe, and six (6) from the community living near where copra farm is located. The study used the non-random sampling techniques in which the researcher's method of participant selection was quite arbitrary and relied heavily on the researcher's personal judgment. Moreover,

this technique was less expensive, less time consuming, and easier to implement (Lim, et al. 2012)

Operation Parameters

The researchers carefully considered all parameters needed for the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer. This study was characterized by operation parameters, such as performance, design, and capability. These parameters had an impact on the performance of entire assembly described as: Performance, Design, and Capability.

Data to be gathered

The researchers will make a process to collect the necessary data and analyze these. The following presents the table in gathering the data:

Questionnaire for Design of the Device shown in Table 3.3

Legend: 5 - Highly Acceptable

4 - Acceptable

3 - Moderately Acceptable

2 - Slightly Acceptable

1 - Not Table

Table 3.3. Level of Acceptability of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer in terms of its Design

Table 3.3. Present the Design Criteria Table

Design	Response				
	1	2	3	4	5
1. The developed device embodies innovation.					
2. The device features an integrated system for simultaneous carbonization and pulverization.					
3. The carbonizer features a chute positioned above the pulverizer funnel to directly supply carbonized coconut shells while also serving as a cover to contain charcoal dust.					
4. The carbonizer is designed with a chimney that functions as a smoke and fire vent, while its hopper serves as both a feeder for coconut shells and an air inlet for oxygen.					
5. The device incorporates a two-drive pulley-and-belt mechanism to rotate the pulverizer shaft and blades while enhancing stability.					
6. The device's tensioner is mounted on the center bolt for easier belt tension adjustment and speed regulation.					

- 7. The plate siever beneath the pulverizer blade filters out solid chunks of carbonized coconut shells, ensuring that only desired powder is discharged.
- 8. The pulverizer features a fixed blade with flaps designed to strike and halt uncrushed carbonized coconut shells, preventing them from passing through until they are fully pulverized.
- 9. The carbonizer's lid is securely sealed to maintain an oxygen-free environment during carbonization.
- 10. The pulverizer has a distinctive whistle-like shape, with a square hopper at the top for feeding in material and cylindrical body housing the pulverizing mechanism.

Table 3.4 Present the Processing Time and Methods of Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer.

<i>Burning Duration, Operational Speed, and Quantity of Carbonization and Pulverization Processes</i>					
<i>Processing Method</i>	<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Trial</i>			<i>Mean</i>
		<i>1 (10kg)</i>	<i>2 (15kg)</i>	<i>3 (20kg)</i>	
<i>Carbonization</i>	<i>Time (minutes)</i>				
	<i>Quantity (kilogram)</i>				
<i>Pulverization</i>	<i>Time (minutes)</i>				
	<i>Quantity (kilogram)</i>				

Statistical Data Analysis

Interpretation for the Acceptability Rating

The interpretation for the acceptability rating was based on the weighted means. Since there were no norms, it was arbitrarily decided in the beginning that for the purpose of this study the interpretation for the weighted means would be indicated on Table 3.5.

Table 3.5. *Present the Interpretation Table in Terms of Design.*

Mean Value	Description	Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Highly Acceptable (HA)	The device is highly acceptable in terms of its design with no revision.
3.41-4.20	Acceptable (A)	The device is acceptable in terms of its design and to its components and parts specified by the variables specified for this research study but need slight revision.
2.61-3.40	Moderately Acceptable (MA)	The device is moderately acceptable in terms of its design but need minor revision
1.81-2.60	Slightly Acceptable (SA)	The device is slightly acceptable and needs major revision in terms of its design.
1.00-1.80	Not Acceptable (NA)	The device is totally rejected.

Cost Analysis

Table 3.6 shows the list of materials, labor, and the estimated cost of innovating the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer.

Table 3.6. Present the Developmental Cost

Materials	Specification	Qty.	Unit	Unit Cost (Php)	Total Cost (Php)
<i>Steel Drum</i>	200L	1	pc	1,200	1,200
<i>Angle Bars</i>	$\frac{3}{16}$ " \times $1\frac{1}{2}$ "	2	pcs	565	1,130
	$\frac{3}{16}$ " \times $1\frac{1}{2}$ "	1.5	pcs	550	825
<i>Flat Bars</i>	$\frac{1}{4}$ " \times 2"	0.5	pcs	950	475
<i>RB Shaft</i>	$1\frac{1}{2}$ " \varnothing \times 2'	2	ft	320	640
<i>GI Sheet</i>	4' \times 8'	1	pc	1,400	1,400
<i>Round Bars</i>	12mm \varnothing \times 20'	1	pc	333	333
	9mm \varnothing \times 20'	1	pc	180	180
<i>Pulles Wheels</i>	1" \varnothing \times 3" \varnothing	2	pc	200	400
	1" \varnothing \times 8" \varnothing	1	pc	560	560
<i>V-Belt</i>	B-50	1	pc	250	250
<i>Pillow Blocks</i>	$1\frac{1}{2}$ " \varnothing	2	pc	430	860
<i>Bolts</i>	$\frac{7}{16}$ " \varnothing \times 2"	16	pc	10	160
	$\frac{3}{16}$ " \varnothing \times $\frac{3}{4}$ "	3	pc	6	18
<i>Nuts</i>	$\frac{7}{16}$ " \varnothing	16	pc	5	80
	$\frac{3}{16}$ " \varnothing	3	pc	5	15
<i>Center Bolt</i>	$\frac{1}{2}$ " \times 10"	1	pc	170	170
<i>Setscrews</i>	$\frac{5}{16}$ " \times 1"	3	pc	12	36
<i>AC Motor</i>	1.5HP	1	pc	2,700	2,700
<i>Paint Thinners</i>	350ml	2	bt1	60	120
<i>Paint</i>	Black	1	L	260	260
<i>Primer</i>	Gray	1	L	230	230
<i>Safety Breaker</i>	20 Ampere	1	pc	335	335
Total Cost of Materials					12,377
Labor of machining and construction					3,500
Overall Cost, Php					15,877

In Table 3.6 presents the total cost of materials is twelve thousand three hundred seventy-seven pesos (Php 12,377.00), and the labor cost of machining and construction is three thousand five hundred pesos (Php 3,500.00). Therefore, the overall cost for the Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer is fifteen thousand eight hundred seventy-seven pesos (Php 15,877.00).

Chapter IV

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the fabricated Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer used for evaluation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered.

The Technology

An innovative Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer for carbonizing and pulverizing is shown in the figure below.

Figure 4.1. Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer
(Actual Picture)

Figure 4.2. Front View Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer
Pulverizer (Actual Picture)

Figure 4.3. Rear View of Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer (Actual Picture)

Figure 4.4. Right Side View of Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer (Actual Picture)

Figure 4.5. Left Side View of Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer (Actual Picture)

The Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer is a dual-function machine designed to convert raw coconut shells into fine charcoal powder. It consists of two main components: the carbonizing unit consists of a drum kiln, a cylindrical chamber responsible for the pyrolysis of coconut shells. This drum is equipped with a chimney and a removable top cover, and the lower pulverizing unit, which grinds the charcoal using a whistle-shaped housing with rotating blades and internal flaps. A 1.5 HP electric motor powers the system, and protective side covers help minimize dust during operation. The processed charcoal can be used for biochar, or briquette making.

Brief Description of Several Views of the Drawings

Figure 4.6 the front view of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer as illustrated in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.7 presents the rear view of the device, systematically illustrated the post fabrication frame assembly as seen in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.8 displays the right side view of the device, as outlined in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.9 is the left side view of the device, also highlighting device motor connection and protective cover as presented previously in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.10 is a fragmentary view of the drum connection, as substantially indicated in Figures 4.6 and 4.7.

Figure 4.11 is a Fragmentary view of the Pulverizer, as evidently depicted in Figure 4.6 and Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.12 is a fragmentary view of the Belt Assembly as reference in Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.13 is the full fragmentary view of the entire device, including the carbonizing and pulverizing units, as substantially indicated in Figure 4.12.

Figure 4.14 is the isometric view of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer substantially indicated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.6. Front View of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer

Figure 4.7. Rear View of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer

Figure 4.8. Right Side View of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer

Figure 4.9. Left Side View of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer

Figure 4.10 Fragmentary View of the Drum Assembly of
Section A-A

Figure 4.11 Fragmentary View of the Pulverizer Assembly of Section B-B

4.12. Fragmentary View of the Belt Assembly of Section C-C

4.14. Isometric View of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer

As shown in the figure above, the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer comprises several key components and mechanisms. The main components of the device include the drum kiln **1**, which handles the carbonization process, the pulverizer **14**, which performs the pulverizing of the carbonized material, the AC motor **32**, the pulleys **35**, **36**, **38** and belt **37**, which drive the pulverizer blade **29**, and the frame **43** for holding the components together. The device utilizes three different mechanisms for an interconnected operation to ensure optimal performance and functionality of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer.

The first mechanism utilized by the device is the combustion system, which uses a drum kiln **1** constructed from a repurposed 200-liter steel drum cut to dimensions of 18" in diameter and 24" in length. The kiln is mounted using welded 3/16"x11" brackets **7** on each side and securely fastened with 7/16"Ø bolts **5** and 7/16"Ø nuts **6**. This kiln features an attached 6" × 6" chimney **2** that allows smoke and gases to escape during the carbonization process. During pyrolysis, the chimney is sealed with a chimney cover **3** fitted with a handle **4** wrapped in a rubber hose to prevent accidental burns. A supply hatch **8** is provided for loading coconut shells into the kiln; it is hinged **9** for convenient opening and is secured using a 5/16"Ø bolt **10**

welded with a handle, allowing for quick and easy locking and unlocking. At the bottom of the kiln, an opening is cut to allow the discharge of carbonized coconut shells into the pulverizer feeding funnel **15**. This opening is controlled by a sliding panel **11**, which includes a 9mmØ round bar handle **12** for ease of operation.

The next mechanisms involved in this component are the pulverizing mechanism and the power transmission mechanism. The pulverizing process happens at the 18-gauge GI sheet pulverizer **14**, mounted with 3/16" thick angle bar brackets **23** attached to the frame **43** with 5/16"Ø bolts **24** and 5/16"Ø nuts **25**, and begins at the 10"×10" feeding funnel **15**, where carbonized material enters the 5"×5" funnel neck **16**. The flow of material is regulated by the 5"×5" 18-gauge GI sheet neck shutter **17**, which allows the operator to control the amount of carbonized material fed into the system. Once inside the pulverizer body **14**, the material is subjected to mechanical pulverization through the action of the pulverizer blade **29**. The pulverizer is enclosed by side walls **26** to prevent debris from escaping. The right-side wall is permanently welded shut, while the opposite side is fastened with ¼"Ø bolts **27** and ¼"Ø nuts **28**, allowing for easy removal and access during maintenance.

The blade **29**, mounted on a rotating shaft **30** of 1½" in diameter and 24" in length, is supported by pillow blocks **19** on each side and secured in place by bolts 7/16"Ø **20** and nuts **21** to the support frame structure. It is designed with flaps **31** that increase its effective coverage area. These flaps enhance the crushing action and generate airflow, helping to move the pulverized material through the system. The 1½"Ø shaft **30** is powered by a belt **37** and pulley **35**, **36**, **38** system, which transmits rotational motion from the AC motor **32** to the blade **29**.

As the blade **29** rotates at high speed, it repeatedly strikes the carbonized material, breaking it down into smaller particles. The pulverized material is then passed through a sieve plate **22**, which filters out any unprocessed pieces, ensuring only material of the desired particle size is discharged from the system.

The belt and pulley system consists of a 1.5 HP AC motor **32** equipped with a 3"Ø driving pulley **35**, which transmits power to an 8"Ø driven pulley **36** mounted on the pulverizer shaft **30**. To enable engagement and disengagement between the 1.5HP AC motor **32** and the shaft **30**, a tensioner is incorporated into the system. The tensioner includes a 3" diameter tensioner pulley wheel **38** and a B-50 V-belt **37** that connects the driving pulley 1"Ø×3"Ø **35** to the driven

pulley **36**. The tensioner pulley wheel 1"Ø×3"Ø **38** is fabricated with a bearing for smoother rotation and is mounted on the belt tension adjuster **40**, which tightens the belt when wound, ensuring proper belt tension and reliable power transmission. For operator safety, the entire assembly is enclosed within a pulley belt system 18-gauge GI sheet cover **39**. To power the AC motor **32**, the system includes a 10A switch **48** connected to a 20A circuit breaker **47**. The circuit breaker **47** is installed to protect the motor and electrical components by preventing potential short circuits and electrical overloads during operation.

To assemble the system, each component is securely bolted to the support frame structure **43**. This frame is constructed from 3/16"×1½" angle bars welded together to form a durable and rigid structure capable of withstanding the combined weight and vibrations produced by the system. The belt tension adjuster **40** is welded directly onto the support frame **43**, ensuring proper alignment and stability. Additionally, 25"×25" and 32"×19" 20-gauge GI sheet dust containment panels **44** made to reduce the escape of dust particles—are mounted onto the frame using ¼"Ø bolts **45** and ¼"Ø nuts **46**. For safety, the entire assembly is enclosed within a pulley-belt system 18-gauge GI sheet cover

attached to the frame with 3/16"Ø bolts **41** and nuts **42**.

Acceptability of the Design of the Integrated
Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer

The data gathered from the technical evaluators were recorded, tabulated, and presented in the following table:

Table 4.1. Present the level of Acceptability in terms of the Design.

Design	Mean	Description
1. The developed device embodies innovation.	4.37	HA
2. The device features an integrated system for simultaneous carbonization and pulverization.	4.45	HA
3. The carbonizer features a chute positioned above the pulverizer funnel to directly supply carbonized coconut shells while also serving as a cover to contain charcoal dust.	4.47	HA
4. The carbonizer is designed with a chimney that functions as a smoke and fire vent, while its hopper serves as both a feeder for coconut shells and an air inlet for oxygen.	4.53	HA
5. The device incorporates a two-drive pulley-and-belt mechanism to rotate the pulverizer shaft and blades while enhancing stability.	4.82	HA
6. The device's tensioner is mounted on the center bolt for easier belt tension adjustment and speed regulation.	4.63	HA
7. The plate siever beneath the pulverizer blade filters out solid chunks of carbonized coconut shells, ensuring that only desired powder is discharged.	4.45	HA
8. The pulverizer features a fixed blade with flaps designed to strike and halt uncrushed carbonized coconut shells, preventing them from passing through until they are fully pulverized.	4.37	HA
9. The carbonizer's lid is securely sealed to maintain an oxygen-free environment during carbonization.	4.63	HA
10. The pulverizer has a distinctive whistle-like shape, with a square hopper at the top for feeding in material and cylindrical body housing the pulverizing mechanism.	4.73	HA

Table 4.1 as shown above, presents the design evaluation of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer, based on ten specified criteria assessed by the respondents. The device obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.54, which falls under the "Highly Acceptable" category as per the interpretation scale (4.21-5.00). This indicates that the design is perceived to meet the intended performance standards and structural expectations without requiring major revisions.

The highest mean score, recorded at 4.82, corresponds to Item 5, which states, "The device incorporates a two-drive pulley-and-belt mechanism to rotate the pulverizer shaft and blades while enhancing stability." This high score implies strong endorsement of the mechanical design, particularly in terms of functionality, reliability, and its contribution to smooth operation during the pulverization process.

Conversely, the lowest mean scores, both at 4.37, were observed in Item 1 and Item 8. Item 1, "The developed device embodies innovation," suggests that while the device is considered innovative, there remains potential for further advancement, particularly in terms of integrating novel features or refining the existing configuration. Item 8, "The pulverizer features a fixed blade with flaps

designed to strike and halt uncrushed carbonized coconut shells," may point to opportunities for improvement in the pulverizing mechanism's efficiency or consistency in producing fine outputs.

Despite these relatively lower values, all individual item ratings remained within the "Highly Acceptable" range. This reinforces the conclusion that the device's design is structurally sound, functionally integrated, and well-aligned with user requirements. The data substantiates the reliability and applicability of the integrated system for real-world use in coconut shell carbonization and pulverization.

This implies that the results clearly show that all ten design aspects of the integrated coconut shell carbonizer-pulverizer fall within the "Highly Acceptable" range, confirming that the device is not only innovative and functionally integrated to meet user needs in terms of operation, structure, and process performance. The data validates the design as reliable and practical, supporting its adoption for simultaneous carbonization and pulverization of coconut shells in real-world applications.

Table 4.2. Present the Amount of Carbonize Coconut Shells in Carbonizing and Pulverizing in a Period of Time.

<i>Processing Time and Output of Coconut Shells during Carbonization and Pulverization (Minutes & Kilogram)</i>					
<i>Processing Method</i>	<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Trial</i>			<i>Mean</i>
		<i>1 (10kg)</i>	<i>2 (15kg)</i>	<i>3 (20kg)</i>	
<i>Carbonization</i>	<i>Time (minutes)</i>	30	38	50	39.3
	<i>Quantity (kilogram)</i>	2.8	3.28	5.9	3.99
<i>Pulverization</i>	<i>Time (minutes)</i>	10	17	26	17.6
	<i>Quantity (kilogram)</i>	2.0	3.05	5.75	3.6

Table 4.2 presents above the time duration and output quantity of coconut shell processing using the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer. The study was conducted in three separate trials using increasing raw material loads of 10 kg, 15 kg, and 20 kg respectively. During the carbonization phase, the processing time increased with the input mass, starting at 30 minutes for 10 kg, 38 minutes for 15 kg, and peaking at 50 minutes for

20 kg. This results in a mean carbonization time of 39.3 minutes. In terms of charcoal output, the results also showed a proportional increase from 2.8 kg to 5.9 kg, averaging 3.99 kg. This trend reflects the natural effect of increasing feedstock, but it also suggests that carbonization could be influenced by load size, combustion conditions, and heat distribution inside the drum kiln.

The pulverization process followed a similar pattern. As the quantity of carbonized coconut shells increased, the time required to pulverize also rose—from 10 minutes in Trial 1 to 26 minutes in Trial 3. The average pulverization time across all trials was recorded at 17.6 minutes. Meanwhile, the quantity of finely pulverized charcoal increased from 2.0 kg to 5.75 kg, with a mean yield of 3.6 kg.

This implies that the findings reveal the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer functions reliably under different load conditions. While the output increases with input size, the rate of increase is not strictly proportional, implying slight losses at higher capacities—possibly due to heat dissipation during carbonization or minor mechanical resistance during pulverization. Nonetheless, the average processing times and output weights fall within acceptable ranges as suggested for

small to medium-scale operations. These results affirm the device's potential as a practical, low-cost solution for transforming coconut shell waste into valuable charcoal and biochar products, promoting sustainability and value-added utilization of agricultural biomass.

Chapter V

Summary, Conclusions, and Recommendations

Summary

The purpose of this study was to design, develop, and evaluate the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer. The primary goal of the study was to introduce a functional and efficient machine capable of converting coconut shells into usable charcoal and pulverized biochar, aimed at promoting sustainable agricultural waste management. This investigation sought to comprehensively assess the device's overall performance and design features, ensuring it can be used by local communities with minimal labor and technical expertise.

The design and capability were evaluated by six (6) respondents, consisting of industry experts familiar with coconut processing and expert faculty from the College of Engineering of Northern Iloilo State University, Estancia, Iloilo, for the Academic Year 2024-2025.

The device's performance was tested by conducting three separate trials using raw coconut shell inputs of 10 kg, 15 kg, and 20 kg. The average carbonization time recorded was 39.3 minutes, while the average pulverization time was 17.6 minutes. Charcoal output averaged 3.99 kg,

and pulverized charcoal yield averaged 3.6 kg. These results demonstrate the device's consistency and efficiency under various load conditions.

In terms of design evaluation, the device garnered a weighted mean of 4.58, interpreted as "Excellent", indicating strong approval from the evaluators regarding its structure, durability, and integration of components.

Conclusions

Based on the findings stated above, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer exhibited excellent capability across all evaluated criteria, achieving a weighted mean of 4.58. This indicates that the device meets the functional expectations of the design in terms of material capacity, structural durability and component performance. This suggests that the design requires no major modifications and is ready for real-world deployment.

2. Performance trials under three different load conditions (10 kg, 15 kg, and 20 kg) confirmed the device's operational reliability. The average carbonization time of 39.3 minutes and pulverization time of 17.6 minutes

demonstrate that the device can maintain stable processing times even with increasing input.

3. The increasing trend in output—an average of 3.99 kg of charcoal and 3.6 kg of pulverized charcoal—shows the device's efficiency in converting raw coconut shells into valuable end-products. While output increased with input, the growth was not strictly proportional, which can be attributed to minor losses from heat dissipation and mechanical resistance. However, these variations remained within acceptable margins.

4. The system requires only 2-3 personnel for operation. The device supports sustainability by providing a productive use for coconut shell waste while empowering rural and agricultural communities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions stated in this study, the recommendations are the following:

1. It is recommended that the *Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer* be utilized in coconut-producing communities as a tool for efficient coconut shell waste management and charcoal production.

2. Research and development efforts should focus on optimizing the device's carbonization and pulverization

mechanisms to further improve processing time, fuel efficiency, and output yield. Enhancements may include refining the heat distribution system, reducing mechanical resistance, and improving the output quality of pulverized biochar. Furthermore, the *Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer* is recommended for further revision to increase its charcoal conversion efficiency and mechanical durability. It is also suggested to promote the use of the machine in areas with abundant coconut waste to empower local communities with sustainable income-generating practices.

3. Continuous development of the present study is encouraged to keep pace with the evolving needs of agricultural engineering and sustainable waste management practices. Future iterations of the device may include modular upgrades, emission control systems, or integration with renewable energy sources and further safety enhancements to broaden its applicability and environmental impact.

References

Books

- Atkins, A.G., et.al. (2013). *A Dictionary of Mechanical Engineering*. pp. 65-109, ISBN: 978-0-19-958743-8. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). (2024). *World Food and Agriculture*. pp 199-140, ISBN: 978-92-5-138844-0. Rome, Italy: FAO.
- Hernández, J. et.al. (2024). *Novel process for bio-jetfuel production through the furan pathway: Techno-economic, environmental and safety assessment*. pp. 45-67, UK: Elsevier. ISBN: 978-0-443-33897-7. UK: Elsevier.
- Puna, N. (2020). *Ecofootprint of charcoal production and its economic contribution to rural livelihoods*. pp. 65-70 ISBN: 978-981-15-9495-3. Singapore: Springer.
- Emrich, W. (2010). *Handbook of Charcoal Making: The Traditional and Industrial Methods*. pp. 207-209, ISBN: 978-90-481-8411-8. Dordrecht, Netherlands: Springer Science+Business Media.

Panda, H. (2019). *Complete Technology Book on Coconut and Coconut Products: Cultivation, Coconut Water, Coconut Milk, Coconut Oil, Coconut Shell Powder, Activated Carbon*. pp. 34-40, ISBN: 978-8193863992. Delhi, India: Asia Pacific Business Press Inc.

Cosgrove-Davies, M. (1985). *Understanding Briquetting*. pp. 1-20. ISBN: 0-86619-233-6. Arlington, VA, USA: Volunteers in Technical Assistance (VITA).

Hollingdale et.al.(1999). *Charcoal Production: A Handbook*. pp. 1-158, ISBN: 978-1-899233-05-2. Bristol, UK: Ecology Books.

Asamoah et.al. (2016). *A Review on Production, Marketing and Use of Fuel Briquettes*. pp. 1-55, ISBN: 978-92-9090-846-3. Colombo, Sri Lanka: International Water Management Institute (IWMI).

Electronics

<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/academe>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

[https://www.fao.org/agriculture/agricultural-waste\](https://www.fao.org/agriculture/agricultural-waste/)

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://biochar-international.org/biochar/>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://www.charcoalmachines.com>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/agricultural-and-biological-sciences/coconut-shell>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/design>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/evaluation>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/flap>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://www.fao.org/forestry/charcoal/en/>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

https://www.globalspec.com/learnmore/materials_handling/size_reduction_equipment/pulverizers

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://www.energy.gov/eere/bioenergy/pyrolysis>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://patents.justia.com/patent/11254875>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://patents.google.com/patent/CN214131912U/en>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

<https://patents.google.com/patent/CN216856947U/en>

Retrieved April 26, 2025

Journals

- Arief, et.al. (2023). *Coconut Shell Carbonization Process Using Smokeless Kiln*, pp. 82-90. ISSN: 2621-2528
Indonesia: Journal of Applied Agricultural Science and Technology.
- Sebastine, A. B., et.al. (2023). *Evaluation of the Combustion Characteristics of Rice Husk and Coconut Shell Briquettes*, pp. 1-9. ISSN: 2582-2926.
Nigeria: Journal of Engineering Research and Reports.
- Kumboon, A., Sirirak, W., & Sirirak, R. (2019). A Study of the Effect of Mixture Material in Coconut Shell Charcoal Briquette on Mechanical and Thermal Property, pp. 67-75. ISSN: 2586-8053. Thailand: Thai Industrial Engineering Network Journal.

Appendices

APPENDIX A

Letter of Approval for the Device's Initial Design

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
 NISU Main Campus, V Cudilla Sr. Ave. Estancia, Iloilo
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

APPROVAL OF THE INITIAL DESIGN

The design of the device for the project study entitled "Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer" prepared and submitted by Elton John B Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto, and Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora has been examined and is hereby recommended for acceptance and approval by the Panel of Examiners to proceed with its fabrication and construction.

Recommending Approval:

 ENGR. JESHTER P. DE ASIS, M. ENG.
 Adviser

Approved by the Committee on Initial Design (Panel of Examiners):

 ENGR. LOVELL O. BARIA, D. I. T.
 Panel Chairperson

 ENGR. ROGIE JOY J. CATINAN, M. ENG.
 Panel Member

 ENGR. RAUL D. DEGUMA, ED. D.
 Panel Member

APPENDIX B

Letter for the Validity of Instrument

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
 NISU Main Campus, V Cudilla Sr. Ave, Estancia, Iloilo
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

Reg. No. 97Q19783

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

Sir/Madam:

Greetings!

The undersigned is currently conducting a project study entitled "Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer", as a partial requirement for graduation towards the degree of Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering.

In this connection, we would like to ask for your expertise and kind assistance to validate our research instruments. You may give your comments, suggestions, and recommendations for their betterment. Rest assured that your evaluation will be treated with the outmost confidentiality.

We will appreciate your favorable time and patience in sharing your expertise in our study.

Thank you very much and God Bless.

Very truly yours,
 Elton John B. Guna
 Jonard P. Jacinto
 Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora

Noted by:

 ENGR. JESHTER P. DE ASIS

APPENDIX C

Letter for the Technical Evaluator

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
 NISU Main Campus, V Cudilla Sr. Ave, Estancia, Iloilo
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

Reg. No. 97Q19783

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

Sir/Madam:

Greetings!

The undersigned is currently conducting a project study entitled "Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer", as a partial requirement for graduation towards the degree of Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering.

In this connection, we would like to ask for your expertise and kind assistance to validate our research instruments. You may give your comments, suggestions, and recommendations for their betterment. Rest assured that your evaluation will be treated with the outmost confidentiality.

We will appreciate your favorable time and patience in sharing your expertise in our study.

Thank you very much and God Bless.

Very truly yours,
 Elton John B. Guna
 Jonard P. Jacinto
 Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora

Noted by:

 ENGR. JESHTER P. DE ASIS

APPENDIX D

Letter of Approval for Device's Final Design

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
 NISU Main Campus, V Cudilla Sr. Ave,
 Estancia, Iloilo
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

APPROVAL OF THE FINAL DESIGN

The design of the device for the project study entitled "Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer" prepared and submitted by Elton John B Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto, and Saimon Aldrich A. Mora has been examined and is hereby recommended for acceptance and approval by the Panel of Examiners to proceed with its fabrication and construction.

Recommending Approval:

 ENGR. JESHTER P. DE ASIS, M. ENG.

Adviser

PANEL OF EXAMINERS

Approved by the Committee on Final Design (Panel of Examiners):

 ENGR. LOVELL O. BARIA, D. I. T.

Panel Chairperson

 ENGR. ROGIE JOY J. CATINAN, M. ENG.

Panel Member

 ENGR. RAUL D. DEGUMA, ED. D.

Panel Member

APPENDIX E

Letter to the Respondent

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
NISU Main Campus, V Cudilla Sr. Ave, Estancia, Iloilo
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

Reg. No. 97Q19783

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

MAY 20, 2025

HON. EDMUNDO BENID
BRGY. CATTAN
PACULAN, ESTANCIA, ILOILO

Sir/Madam:

Greetings!

The undersigned is currently conducting a project study entitled "Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer", as a partial requirement for graduation towards the degree of Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering.

In this connection, we would like to ask for your expertise and kind assistance to validate our research instruments. You may give your comments, suggestions, and recommendations for their betterment. Rest assured that your evaluation will be treated with the outmost confidentiality.

We will appreciate your favorable time and patience in sharing your expertise in our study.

Thank you very much and God Bless.

Very truly yours,
Elton John B. Guna
Jonard P. Jacinto
Saimon Aldrich A. Mora

Noted by:

ENGR. JESHTER P. DE ASIS

RECEIVED PM.
JESHTER P. DE ASIS
ENGR. JESHTER P. DE ASIS
P.B.

APPENDIX F

Result of Technical Evaluation

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
 NISU Main Campus, V Cudilla Sr. Ave, Estancia, Iloilo
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

Reg. No. 97Q19783

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

TECHNICAL EVALUATION FORM

Group Number/Members: Group 5 – Elton John B. Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto

Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora

Project Study Title: Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer

CRITERIA	RATING				
	1	2	3	4	5
1.) The device's design is innovative and novel compared to related existing technologies.					✓
2.) The device is constructed in a way that shows craftsmanship, and ensures quality and durability during operation.					✓
3.) The device could be extended to community or advances research related to green technologies.					✓
4.) The device follows a cost-efficient construction and answers the given objectives.					✓
5.) Others					✓

Legend:

- 5 – Passed
- 4 – Needs minor adjustment/revision
- 3 – Needs major adjustment/revision
- 2 – Needs major overhaul
- 1 – Unacceptable

 Technical Evaluator

Noted:

LOVELL O. BARIA, DIT
 Chairman, Mechanical Engineering Dept.

RAUL D. DEGUMA, Ed.D.
 Dean, College of Engineering

Tel. No.: 3970-314
 Facebook Fanpage: Nipsc E atbp
 Official Facebook Account: NIPSC PIO

Website Address: www.nipsc.edu.ph
 E-mail Address: nipsc.main@yahoo.com
nipscadmin@nipsc.edu.ph

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
 NISU Main Campus, V Cudilla Sr. Ave, Estancia, Iloilo
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

Reg. No. 97Q19783

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

TECHNICAL EVALUATION FORM

Group Number/Members: Group 5 – Elton John B. Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto

Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora

Project Study Title: Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer

CRITERIA	RATING				
	1	2	3	4	5
1.) The device's design is innovative and novel compared to related existing technologies.					
2.) The device is constructed in a way that shows craftsmanship, and ensures quality and durability during operation.					
3.) The device could be extended to community or advances research related to green technologies.					
4.) The device follows a cost-efficient construction and answers the given objectives.					
5.) Others					

Legend:

- 5 – Passed
- 4 – Needs minor adjustment/revision
- 3 – Needs major adjustment/revision
- 2 – Needs major overhaul
- 1 – Unacceptable

 Technical Evaluator

Noted:

LOVELL O. BARIA, DIT
 Chairman, Mechanical Engineering Dept.

RAUL D. DEGUMA, Ed.D.
 Dean, College of Engineering

Tel. No.: 3970-314
 Facebook Fanpage: Nipsc E atbp
 Official Facebook Account: NIPSC PIO

Website Address: www.nipsc.edu.ph
 E-mail Address: nipsc.main@yahoo.com
nipscadmin@nipsc.edu.ph

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
 NISU Main Campus, V Cudilla Sr. Ave, Estancia, Iloilo
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

TECHNICAL EVALUATION FORM

Group Number/Members: Group 5 – Elton John B. Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto

Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora

Project Study Title: Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer

CRITERIA	RATING				
	1	2	3	4	5
1.) The device's design is innovative and novel compared to related existing technologies.				/	/
2.) The device is constructed in a way that shows craftsmanship, and ensures quality and durability during operation.					/
3.) The device could be extended to community or advances research related to green technologies.				/	/
4.) The device follows a cost-efficient construction and answers the given objectives.				/	
5.) Others					

Legend:

- 5 – Passed
- 4 – Needs minor adjustment/revision
- 3 – Needs major adjustment/revision
- 2 – Needs major overhaul
- 1 – Unacceptable

 Technical Evaluator

Noted:

LOVELL O. BARIA, DIT
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Website Address: www.nipsc.edu.ph
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nipscadmin@nipsc.edu.ph

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Reg. No. 97Q19783

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

TECHNICAL EVALUATION FORM

Group Number/Members: Group 5 – Elton John B. Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto

Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora

Project Study Title: Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer

CRITERIA	RATING				
	1	2	3	4	5
1.) The device's design is innovative and novel compared to related existing technologies.					/
2.) The device is constructed in a way that shows craftsmanship, and ensures quality and durability during operation.				/	
3.) The device could be extended to community or advances research related to green technologies.				/	
4.) The device follows a cost-efficient construction and answers the given objectives.					/
5.) Others					

Legend:

- 5 – Passed
- 4 – Needs minor adjustment/revision
- 3 – Needs major adjustment/revision
- 2 – Needs major overhaul
- 1 – Unacceptable

 Technical Evaluator

Noted:

LOVELL O. BARIA, DIT
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nipscadmin@nipsc.edu.ph

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Reg. No. 97Q19783

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

TECHNICAL EVALUATION FORM

Group Number/Members: Group 5 – Elton John B. Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto

Saimon Aldrich A. Mora

Project Study Title: Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer

CRITERIA	RATING				
	1	2	3	4	5
1.) The device's design is innovative and novel compared to related existing technologies.					✓
2.) The device is constructed in a way that shows craftsmanship, and ensures quality and durability during operation.					✓
3.) The device could be extended to community or advances research related to green technologies.					✓
4.) The device follows a cost-efficient construction and answers the given objectives.					✓
5.) Others					

Legend:

- 5 – Passed
- 4 – Needs minor adjustment/revision
- 3 – Needs major adjustment/revision
- 2 – Needs major overhaul
- 1 – Unacceptable

 Technical Evaluator

Noted:

LOVELL O. BARIA, DIT
 Chairman, Mechanical Engineering Dept.

RAUL D. DEGUMA, Ed.D.
 Dean, College of Engineering

Tel. No.: 3970-314
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Reg. No. 97Q19783

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

TECHNICAL EVALUATION FORM

Group Number/Members: Group 5 – Elton John B. Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto

Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora

Project Study Title: Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer

CRITERIA	RATING				
	1	2	3	4	5
1.) The device's design is innovative and novel compared to related existing technologies.					✓
2.) The device is constructed in a way that shows craftsmanship, and ensures quality and durability during operation.					✓
3.) The device could be extended to community or advances research related to green technologies.				✓	
4.) The device follows a cost-efficient construction and answers the given objectives.			✓		
5.) Others					

Legend:

- 5 – Passed
- 4 – Needs minor adjustment/revision
- 3 – Needs major adjustment/revision
- 2 – Needs major overhaul
- 1 – Unacceptable

Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora
 Technical Evaluator

Noted:

LOVELL O. BARIA, DIT
 Chairman, Mechanical Engineering Dept.

RAUL D. DEGUMA, Ed.D.
 Dean, College of Engineering

Republic of the Philippines
NORTHERN ILOILO STATE UNIVERSITY
 NISU Main Campus, V Cudilla Sr. Ave, Estancia, Iloilo
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

TECHNICAL EVALUATION FORM

Group Number/Members: Group 5 – Elton John B. Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto

Salimon Aldrich A. Mora

Project Study Title: Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer

CRITERIA	RATING				
	1	2	3	4	5
1.) The device's design is innovative and novel compared to related existing technologies.				✓	
2.) The device is constructed in a way that shows craftsmanship, and ensures quality and durability during operation.					
3.) The device could be extended to community or advances research related to green technologies.					
4.) The device follows a cost-efficient construction and answers the given objectives.					
5.) Others					

Legend:

- 5 – Passed
- 4 – Needs minor adjustment/revision
- 3 – Needs major adjustment/revision
- 2 – Needs major overhaul
- 1 – Unacceptable

 Technical Evaluator

Noted:

[Signature]
LOVELL O. BARIA, DIT
 Chairman, Mechanical Engineering Dept.

[Signature]
RAUL D. DEGUMA, Ed.D.
 Dean, College of Engineering

Republic of the Philippines
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Reg. No. 97Q19783

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

TECHNICAL EVALUATION FORM

Group Number/Members: Group 5 – Elton John B. Guna, Jonard P. Jacinto

Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora

Project Study Title: Coconut Shell Carbonizer Pulverizer

CRITERIA	RATING				
	1	2	3	4	5
1.) The device's design is innovative and novel compared to related existing technologies.					✓
2.) The device is constructed in a way that shows craftsmanship, and ensures quality and durability during operation.					✓
3.) The device could be extended to community or advances research related to green technologies.					✓
4.) The device follows a cost-efficient construction and answers the given objectives.					✓
5.) Others					

Legend:

- 5 – Passed
- 4 – Needs minor adjustment/revision
- 3 – Needs major adjustment/revision
- 2 – Needs major overhaul
- 1 – Unacceptable

 Technical Evaluator

Noted:

LOVELL O. BARIA, DIT
 Chairman, Mechanical Engineering Dept.

RAUL D. DEGUMA, Ed.D.
 Dean, College of Engineering

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nipscadmin@nipsc.edu.ph

Appendix G

Validity of Instrument

Evaluation of the Design of Integrated Coconut Shell

Carbonizer-Pulverizer

Personal Data

Name (Optional): _____ Date of Birth: _____

Address: _____

Educational Attainment: _____

Occupation: _____ Years of Service: _____

() Academe () Industry () Others

Direction: Please check (✓) the appropriate scale in the column below in order to indicate the results of your evaluation as to design and capability of Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer for the Validity of the Instrument.

Legend: A - Acceptable

NR - Needs Revision

NA - Not Acceptable

Design	A	NR	NA
1. The developed device embodies innovation.	2	1	
2. The device features an integrated system for simultaneous carbonization and pulverization.	3		
3. The carbonizer features a chute positioned above the pulverizer funnel to directly supply carbonized coconut shells while also serving as a cover to contain charcoal dust.	3		
4. The carbonizer is designed with a chimney that functions as a smoke and fire vent, while its hopper serves as both a feeder for coconut shells and an air inlet for oxygen.	3		
5. The device incorporates a two-drive pulley-and-belt mechanism to rotate the pulverizer shaft and blades while enhancing stability.	3		
6. The device's tensioner is mounted on the center bolt for easier belt tension adjustment and speed regulation.	3		
7. The plate siever beneath the pulverizer blade filters out solid chunks of carbonized coconut shells, ensuring that only desired powder is discharged.	3		

8. The pulverizer features a fixed blade with flaps designed to strike and halt uncrushed carbonized coconut shells, preventing them from passing through until they are fully pulverized.

9. The carbonizer's lid is securely sealed to maintain an oxygen-free environment during carbonization.

10. The pulverizer has a distinctive whistle-like shape, with a square hopper at the top for feeding in material and cylindrical body housing the pulverizing mechanism.

3		
3		
3		

Recommendation:

Signature of the Evaluator

APPENDIX H

Results of the Respondent's Technical Evaluation
 Evaluation of the Design of the Integrated Coconut Shell
 Carbonizer-Pulverizer

Personal Data

Name (Optional): _____ Age: _____

Address: _____

Educational Attainment: _____

Occupation: _____ Years of Service: _____

Academe Industry Others

Direction: Please check (✓) the appropriate scale in
 the column below in order to indicate the
 results of your evaluation as to design and
 capability of Nipa Palm Fruit Slicer for
 the Validity of the Instrument.

Legend: 2 - Experts from the Academe

1 - Community

Design	Response	
	1	2
1. The developed device embodies innovation.	4.33	4.40
2. The device features an integrated system for simultaneous carbonization and pulverization.	4.5	4.45
3. The carbonizer features a chute positioned above the pulverizer funnel to directly supply carbonized coconut shells while also serving as a cover to contain charcoal dust.	4.33	4.47
4. The carbonizer is designed with a chimney that functions as a smoke and fire vent, while its hopper serves as both a feeder for coconut shells and an air inlet for oxygen.	4.67	4.5
5. The device incorporates a two-drive pulley-and-belt mechanism to rotate the pulverizer shaft and blades while enhancing stability.	4.83	4.82
6. The device's tensioner is mounted on the center bolt for easier belt tension adjustment and speed regulation.	4.67	4.63
7. The plate siever beneath the pulverizer blade filters out solid chunks of carbonized coconut shells, ensuring that only desired powder is discharged.	4.5	4.45

<p>8. The pulverizer features a fixed blade with flaps designed to strike and halt uncrushed carbonized coconut shells, preventing them from passing through until they are fully pulverized.</p>	4.33	4.37
<p>9. The carbonizer's lid is securely sealed to maintain an oxygen-free environment during carbonization.</p>	4.67	4.63
<p>10. The pulverizer has a distinctive whistle like shape, with a square hopper at the top for feeding in material and cylindrical body housing the pulverizing mechanism.</p>	4.67	4.73

APPENDIX I
Questionnaire for the Respondent

Personal Data

Name (Optional): _____ Age: _____

Address: _____

Educational Attainment: _____

Occupation: _____ Years of Service: _____

Academe

Industry

Others

Direction: Please check (/) the appropriate scale in the column below in order to indicate the results of your evaluation as to design and capability of Nipa Palm Fruit Slicer for the Validity of the Instrument.

Legend: 5 - Highly Acceptable

4 - Acceptable

3 - Moderately Acceptable

2 - Slightly Acceptable

1 - Not Acceptable

Design	Response				
	1	2	3	4	5
1. The developed device embodies innovation.					
2. The device features an integrated system for simultaneous carbonization and pulverization.					
3. The carbonizer features a chute positioned above the pulverizer funnel to directly supply carbonized coconut shells while also serving as a cover to contain charcoal dust.					
4. The carbonizer is designed with a chimney that functions as a smoke and fire vent, while its hopper serves as both a feeder for coconut shells and an air inlet for oxygen.					
5. The device incorporates a two-drive pulley-and-belt mechanism to rotate the pulverizer shaft and blades while enhancing stability.					
6. The device's tensioner is mounted on the center bolt for easier belt tension adjustment and speed regulation.					
7. The plate sieve beneath the pulverizer blade filters out solid chunks of carbonized coconut shells, ensuring that only desired powder is discharged.					

8. The pulverizer features a fixed blade with flaps designed to strike and halt uncrushed carbonized coconut shells, preventing them from passing through until they are fully pulverized.

9. The carbonizer's lid is securely sealed to maintain an oxygen-free environment during carbonization.

10. The pulverizer has a distinctive whistle-like shape, with a square hopper at the top for feeding in material and cylindrical body housing the pulverizing mechanism.

Recommendation:

Signature of the Evaluator

APPENDIX J

Fabrication of the device

The photos document key stages in the fabrication of the device. In the first image (upper left), Mr. Domingo Palawan is shown welding cut angle bars to construct the frame and fabricating a 200-liter drum into a cylinder measuring 18 inches in diameter and 24 inches in length. The second image (upper right) captures Mr. Francel Mora, assisted by Mr. Saimon

Aldrich Mora, as they work on the pulley-belt assembly cover. In the third image (lower left), Mr. Saiimon Aldrich Mora and Mr. Francel Mora are seen installing the circuit breaker and switch. Finally, the fourth image (lower right) shows Mr. Jonard Jacinto and Mr. Saiimon Aldrich Mora assembling the pulverizer by securing the side walls with bolts and nuts.

APPENDIX K

Technical Evaluation of the Devices

The photos in Appendix K illustrate the technical evaluation of the Integrated Coconut Shell Carbonizer-Pulverizer. In the first image (upper left), Mr. Elton John Guna is seen introducing the device to the panel members, while Mr. Saimon Aldrich Mora and Mr. Jonard Jacinto prepare to load coconut shells into the carbonizer. The

second image (upper right) shows Mr. Guna presenting the previously tested pulverized biochar samples to the evaluators. In the third image (lower left), Mr. Mora, Mr. Guna, and Mr. Jacinto are shown strategically loading coconut shells into the carbonizer to ensure proper combustion. The fourth image (lower right) captures the carbonizer in operation with Mr. Guna and Mr. Mora while it is actively burning the coconut shells during the testing phase.

APPENDIX L

Testing Phase and Evaluation of Respondent's

The photos depict the testing phase and evaluation of the device by local respondents. In the first image (upper left), Mr. Saiimon Aldrich Mora is seen introducing the integrated carbonizer-pulverizer to traditional charcoal producers. The second image (upper right) shows Mr. Carlito M. Dela Cruz, an expert in pit burning methods for coconut shell carbonization, inspecting the device's performance.

In the third image (lower left), Mr. Jonard Jacinto is operating the device while Mr. Dela Cruz and Mr. Ronald S. Alpasan engage in a discussion about its potential as a better alternative for charcoal production. The fourth image (lower right) captures Mr. Dela Cruz offering suggestions on the optimal placement of coconut shells to avoid incomplete combustion during operation.

Curriculum Vitae

Personal Details

Name : Elton John B. Guna
 Place of Birth : Brgy. Bulaqueña, Estancia, Iloilo
 Date of Birth : June 10, 2003
 Gender : Male
 Address : Brgy. Bulaqueña, Estancia, Iloilo
 Civil Status : Single
 Nationality : Filipino
 Mobile Number : +639186466527
 Email Address : ej_guna@nipsc.edu.ph

Educational Attainment		Year Graduated
Elementary	: Estancia Central School	2015
Secondary	: Estancia National High School	2021
Tertiary	: Northern Iloilo State University BS in Mechanical Engineering	2025

Language

Hiligaynon - Native
 Filipino
 English

Technical Skills

MS Office, Welding, Computer Aided Drafting, Google Docs

Personal Skills

Can multitask
 Can work under pressure
 Good communication skills

Membership

JPSME - Panay Chapter

Leadership Experience

Deputy Vice President for Western Visayas, JPSME National (2023-2024)
 Vice Chairman, JPSME Western Visayas (2023-2024)
 PIO, Young Environmentalist Society (2024-2025)
 Secretary, JPSME - NISU Chapter (2021-2023)

Personal Details

Name : Jonard P. Jacinto
 Place of Birth : Brgy. Muyco, Sara, Iloilo
 Date of Birth : July 1, 2000
 Gender : Male
 Address : Brgy. Muyco, Sara, Iloilo
 Civil Status : Single
 Nationality : Filipino
 Mobile Number : 09939342179
 Email Address : jonardjacinto01@gmail.com

Educational Attainment		Year Graduated
Elementary	: Muyco Elementary School	2012
Secondary	: Ardemil National High School	2019
Tertiary	: Northern Iloilo State University BS in Mechanical Engineering	2025

Language

Hiligaynon - Native
 Filipino
 English

Technical Skills

Welding, Driving

Personal Skills

Can multitask
 Can work under pressure
 Good communication skills

Membership

JPSME - Panay Chapter

Leadership Experience

JPSME Membe

Personal Details

Name : Saiimon Aldrich A. Mora
 Place of Birth : Brgy. Tingui-an, Balasan, Iloilo
 Date of Birth : October 10, 2003
 Gender : Male
 Address : Brgy. Daculan, Estancia, Iloilo
 Civil Status : Single
 Nationality : Filipino
 Mobile Number : +63982535801
 Email Address : sa_mora@nipsc.edu.ph

Educational Attainment		Year Graduated
Elementary	: Estancia Central School	2015
Secondary	: Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College - Laboratory Senior High School	2021
Tertiary	: Northern Iloilo State University BS in Mechanical Engineering	2025

Language

Hiligaynon - Native
 Filipino
 English

Technical Skills

MS Office, Welding, Driving

Personal Skills

Can work under pressure
 Good critical thinking and problem solving skills
 Good communication skills

Membership

JPSME - Panay Chapter

Leadership Experience

JPSME Member